

UNLOCKING DATA

Canada

DESIGN-BASED IMPLEMENTATION RESEARCH REPORT: CYCLE 2

AN APPLIED DESIGN-BASED IMPLEMENTATION RESEARCH FRAMEWORK ON FOUNDATIONAL LEARNING IN CAMEROON

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About the Unlocking Data Initiative

The Unlocking Data Initiative is a community of practice that connects African scholars, NGOs, national statistics offices, and policymakers to improve access to and use of education data. The **Unlocking Data: Scaling Uses and Users of Education Data** project is a collaborative work led by Zizi Afrique Foundation and supported by Education Sub-Saharan Africa, eBase Africa, and the University of Malawi's Centre for Education Research and Training (CERT). The latter project, which is being implemented in Cameroon, Kenya, and Malawi, aims to scale up data use and users to address the knowledge gap on how to adaptively scale the effective use of existing education data by policymakers and researchers in Africa.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

CoP	Community of Practice
EMIS	Education Management Information System
SIGE	Système d'Information et de Gestion de l'Éducation
FLN	Foundational Literacy and Numeracy
NIS	National Institute of Statistics
KAP	Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice
MINEDUB	Ministry of Basic Education
PWD	Persons with Disabilities
UCCC	United Councils and Cities of Cameroon
DBIR	Design-Based Implementation Research

Executive summary

This report outlines the outcomes of the second cycle of the design-based implementation research (DBIR) process in Cameroon, building on the foundation laid in Cycle 1. While Cycle 1 successfully established regional Communities of Practice (CoPs) in the Centre and Northwest Regions, Cycle 2 focused on deepening their practical operation and co-creating actionable frameworks for data-driven decision-making. A key methodological addition in this cycle was the systematic administration of pre- and post-workshop Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAP) surveys at both workshop sites, providing the first empirical, participant-level evidence of the initiative's immediate impact. Sections 4–7 set out the key activities, findings, adaptations, and preliminary outcomes from Cycle 2.

The primary activities of this cycle were the inaugural regional workshops, which used a novel “clinic-to-workshop” model. In the Northwest, this culminated in the ratification of the Bamenda Charter, a binding regional framework featuring a “Safe Harbour” ethics compact and an “offline first” data architecture mandate. In both regions, stakeholders defined and adopted formal Regional Learning Agendas, translating broad collaboration goals into specific, priority research questions. Workshop participants in Bamenda (n=37) and Yaoundé (n=26) represented a diverse cross-section of Civil Society Organisations, Ministry officials, researchers, teachers, and local government actors, many of whom had no prior experience of structured data collaboration. The pre- and post-workshop KAP surveys provided participant-level evidence of short-term changes associated with the workshops.

Cycle 2 generated critical insights that confirmed and deepened Cycle 1 findings. It revealed severe evidence voids on priority issues such as teacher motivation and disability inclusion, and exposed systemic data ecosystem failures, including time-lagged EMIS/SIGE data and a critical gap in data literacy at sub-national levels, a gap now empirically substantiated by pre-workshop KAP data, showing that the majority of participants across both sites entered the workshops with very low to low self-assessed knowledge of key data systems and methodologies. Importantly, the cycle demonstrated successful adaptive management, with project activities directly responding to Cycle 1's identified challenges of trust deficits and fragmentation through innovative mechanisms such as the Traffic Light evidence assessment and structured data sharing protocols.

The key outcomes of this cycle are the transition of the CoPs from launched platforms into governed, agenda-setting entities with a demonstrably engaged and increasingly competent membership. This sets a robust foundation for Cycle 3, which must focus on generating the missing evidence, building core data competencies informed by the specific gaps identified in the KAP surveys, and piloting practical tools to transform these agendas into actionable insights to improve foundational learning outcomes in Cameroon.

1. Context and recap of DBIR Cycle 1

Cycle 1 of the DBIR (September 2025) established the foundational architecture for collaborative data use in Cameroon's education sector ([Fotso et al., 2025](#)). Its primary achievement was the operationalisation of two regional Communities of Practice (CoPs) in the Centre and Northwest Regions, led by the Ministry of Basic Education (MINEDUB) Regional Delegates. Key outputs included a co-created stakeholder manifesto and stronger engagement among MINEDUB, INS, and civil society actors.

Cycle 1 also identified four systemic barriers: a fragmented data landscape, significant capacity gaps among sub-national actors, a trust deficit between government and research institutions, and a data system oriented more towards administrative inputs than learning outcomes. Its concluding next steps called for thematic data reflection sessions, the synthesis of regional findings, and a national reflection event to deepen the work.

Against this backdrop, Cycle 2 was designed to address these barriers and advance the agreed next steps, moving the CoPs from initial establishment to more substantive operations.

2. Cycle 2 objectives and methodological approach

2.1. Objectives

Building on the foundations laid in Cycle 1, DBIR Cycle 2 sought to move the regional CoPs from their initial establishment towards more structured, operational forms of collaboration. Its objectives were to:

- Facilitate deeper, thematic reflection to co-create Regional Learning Agendas.
- Conduct an “Evidence Rush” to map existing data against priority questions and identify critical gaps.
- Develop and ratify regional frameworks (e.g., charters, principles) to guide data sharing, ethics, and collaboration.
- Establish formal governance structures (Steering Committees, Technical Working Groups) for the CoPs.
- Foster local ownership and adaptation of data tools and processes to the distinct realities of the Centre and Northwest regions.

2.2. Methodological approach

The methodological approach remained grounded in co-creation and iterative learning, but Cycle 2 introduced more structured diagnostic facilitation tools to support practical, systematic learning. At the centre of the design was the “Clinic-to-Workshop” model, piloted in the Northwest and then reflected in the Centre Region process.

- **Pre-workshop stakeholder clinics:** Separate, safe-space sessions were convened for distinct stakeholder groups (Education Officials, Local Governance, Academia, Civil Society) to foster candid perspectives, map data sources and draft initial priorities.
- **Inaugural CoP workshops:** Multi-stakeholder plenary sessions were then used to validate these priorities, conduct the “Evidence Rush,” and formalise shared outputs, including learning agendas and data-use frameworks.
- **The “traffic light” assessment:** A participatory traffic-light assessment was used to classify the status of the evidence for each priority question: Green (evidence considered sufficient), Yellow (evidence existed but required harmonisation), and Red (evidence was absent or too weak to support action).
- **Contextualised framework development:** Rather than applying a single template across both sites, each region co-developed its own governing framework tailored to its local conditions, including the Bamenda Charter in the crisis-affected Northwest and the Yaoundé CoP for the Centre.

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Taken together, this approach positioned Cycle 2 not simply as a workshop series but as a structured process for defining learning priorities, reviewing available evidence, and establishing the governance conditions for sustained collaboration.

3. Key activities

3.1. One-on-one stakeholder consultations

Targeted bilateral consultations with key stakeholders across both regions formed the first substantive step in building functional Communities of Practice. These engagements reached a broad cross-section of actors, including the Catholic and Presbyterian Education Secretariats, the University of Bamenda, the National Institute of Statistics (NIS), and civil society organisations such as Green Partners Association. Each consultation served two purposes: first, to introduce the CoP concept and its value proposition; and second, to secure concrete commitments to participate in the subsequent workshop processes.

These consultations generated three categories of outcome that directly shaped the design of Cycle 2 activities.

- i. First, they generated candid intelligence on data politicisation, access barriers, and institutional scepticism that would have been less likely to surface in a formal plenary setting. These accounts suggested that the trust deficit between government and civil society actors was more acute than Cycle 1 had indicated, with some CSO representatives expressing concern that data they contributed could be used against them rather than in support of shared goals.
- ii. Second, the consultations helped establish relationships of confidence before the workshops, allowing plenary discussions to begin from a stronger foundation of rapport rather than suspicion.
- iii. Third, and critically, the consultations translated into participation with the diverse cohort profile observed at both workshop sites, reflecting the personal commitments secured during these bilateral engagements. In Bamenda, 37.50 per cent of workshop participants reported prior experience with CoP or data-use initiatives, while the remaining 62.50 per cent were new entrants to this space, suggesting that the consultations extended beyond existing networks.

3.2. Ministry consultations and appointment of focal points

Formal consultations with MINEDUB were held at the outset of Cycle 2 to secure the institutional validation and leadership required for the CoP initiative to function as a credible platform for data-driven decision-making. These high-level discussions presented the CoP's objectives, proposed governance arrangements, and alignment with national education priorities, positioning the initiative as a mechanism to strengthen MINEDUB's sub-national data ecosystem rather than as a parallel structure.

The consultations produced three concrete outcomes.

- i. First, MINEDUB provided official institutional validation for the launch of both regional CoPs, conferring the governmental legitimacy needed to convene diverse stakeholders, including those who might be sceptical of NGO-led initiatives.
- ii. Second, MINEDUB appointed the Regional Delegates for the Centre and Northwest Regions as the official focal points and coordinators for their respective CoPs. This embedded the CoP leadership within the government’s administrative hierarchy and helped align the initiative with ministerial direction at the regional level.
- iii. Third, the consultations surfaced an important pre-existing concern among ministry participants regarding the role of civil society organisations in data generation, specifically, a perception that some CSO-produced data may be “sustenance-driven” rather than rigorous. This scepticism was later addressed through the “Safe Harbour” and “Shadow Report” mechanisms in the Bamenda Charter, demonstrating how pre-workshop consultations directly shape workshop design and outputs. The effect of this government anchoring was later visible in the workshop participant profiles: ministry officials and local government actors were strongly represented at both workshops.

3.3. CoP workshop clinics

Before the main plenary workshop, a series of focused clinics was convened to create dedicated safe spaces for distinct stakeholder groups, including education officials, local governance actors, research & academia, and civil society. This Clinic-to-Workshop model was adopted to reduce the risk of dominant voices monopolising discussions and to enable deeper, more candid conversations within peer groups. Within these clinics, participants mapped specific data sources, shared operational challenges such as the physical dangers of data collection in crisis zones, and drafted initial priorities. The outputs from these parallel sessions were synthesised into stakeholder briefs to more systematically inform the main workshop with the perspectives of frontline data producers and users.

The clinics generated four substantive outcome categories.

- i) First, they produced a region-specific mapping of data sources, participants identifying what datasets existed, who controlled access to them, and what practical obstacles, such as connectivity, bureaucratic gatekeeping, and cost, limited their use. In the Northwest, this exercise showed that centralised online reporting via SIGE was structurally inaccessible in many areas, thereby directly informing the Offline-First mandate, which was subsequently reflected in the Bamenda Charter.
- ii) Second, the safe-space format enabled candid disclosure of operational realities that would not have emerged in a mixed-stakeholder setting, including the

physical risks of data collection in crisis-affected communities in the Northwest, and urban-rural disparity in data availability and use in the Centre Region.

- iii) Third, the clinics produced material that fed directly into the Evidence Rush and the formulation of Regional Learning Agendas in the plenary sessions.
- iv) Fourth, the clinic format helped build the inter-stakeholder familiarity and psychological safety needed for more honest collaboration in the plenary sessions, an effect reflected in the post-workshop KAP data showing that 79.31% of Bamenda participants agreed or strongly agreed that the CoP is collaborative rather than bureaucratic in nature, and 93.11% agreed that community-generated data can be reliable ([↑Pambe et al., 2026](#)).

3.4. CoP workshops

Following the preparatory clinics, inaugural CoP workshops were held separately in the Northwest and Centre regions to co-create the core mandate for each regional platform. In the Northwest, the 20-21 November 2025 workshop used an “Evidence Rush” methodology, which led to the ratification of the Bamenda Charter and the formal adoption of a Regional Learning Agenda built around 8 priority research questions. In the Centre region, the 10-11 December 2025 process brought together stakeholders to validate priorities from preparatory clinics and to draft a Regional Learning Agenda together with a data-sharing framework or related principles. Together, these workshops moved the CoPs from conceptual platforms to agenda-setting bodies, with clear, locally owned research priorities to guide data generation and policy dialogue.

3.4.1. Northwest Region - Bamenda workshop (20 - 21 November 2025)

The Bamenda workshop used an “Evidence Rush” methodology, leading to the ratification of the Bamenda Charter and the formal adoption of a Regional Learning Agenda defined by 8 priority research questions. A total of 25 participants completed the pre-workshop survey and 29 completed the post-workshop survey, representing civil society organisations (36%), researchers and academics (24%), teachers and school heads (20%), local authority officials (16%), and MINEDUB officials (4%). Most participants (62.5%) had not previously participated in any data use or CoP initiative related to education, suggesting that the workshop helped introduce a significant new cohort to structured data collaboration ([↑Pambe et al., 2026](#)).

Knowledge gains. Pre and post-workshop survey data indicate substantial gains across four measured competency domains. Before the workshop, most respondents rated themselves at the lower end of the 5 point scale: 81.25% reported very low or low ability to explain the Regional Learning Agenda; 75% reported very low or low knowledge of sources of foundational learning data; 68.75% reported very low or low confidence in reading SIGE dashboards; and 75% reported very low or low understanding of the

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Evidence Rush methodology. After the workshop, the distribution shifted markedly across all four domains. In three areas, the ability to explain the Regional Learning Agenda, knowledge of FL data sources, and understanding of the Evidence Rush – 87.50% of the respondents rated themselves at level 4 or 5, while confidence in reading SIGE dashboards rose to 68.75% at level 4 or 5 post-workshop ([Pambe et al., 2026](#)).

Table 1 below summarises the pre- and post-workshop knowledge shifts for the Bamenda workshop.

Table 1. Knowledge gained from the Bamenda CoP Workshop (NWR)

Competency Domain	Rating Scale (1=Very Low; 5=Very High)				Shift
	1	2	3	4-5	
Ability to explain the regional learning agenda	43.75%	37.50%	12.50%	6.25%	Pre-workshop
	-	-	12.50%	87.50%	Post-workshop ▲
Knowledge of sources of FL data	37.50%	37.50%	12.50%	12.50%	Pre-workshop
	-	-	12.50%	87.50%	Post-workshop ▲
Confidence in reading SIGE dashboards	50.00%	18.75%	31.25%	-	Pre-workshop
	-	-	31.25%	68.75%	Post-workshop ▲
Understanding “Evidence Rush”	50.00%	25.00%	18.75%	6.25%	Pre-workshop
	-	-	12.50%	87.50%	Post-workshop ▲

Mindset shift. The pre-workshop survey (n=24) revealed a generally fair but still uncertain understanding of the FLN data landscape.

Notably, 91.66% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that education data is underutilised at the subnational level due to limited analytical capacity and low trust in data accuracy, while 95.83% agreed or strongly agreed that the overall objective of

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regional CoPs is to improve the use and utility of foundational learning data through collaboration.

Post-workshop responses (n=29) pointed to a stronger collaborative orientation. Specifically, 79.31% agreed or strongly agreed that CoPs are collaborative rather than bureaucratic; 93.11% agreed or strongly agreed that community-generated data can be reliable; and 92.85% agreed or strongly agreed that ethical data sharing improves decision-making outcomes.

Shift in challenges. A qualitative analysis of open-ended challenge responses suggests a shift in the nature of participants' concerns over the course of the workshop.

Before the workshop, concerns centred on uncertainty about where to find data, gaps in basic data literacy skills, and general apprehension about the analysis process itself.

After the workshop, these foundational concerns had largely shifted toward higher-order challenges: obtaining and using data, navigating institutional politics, securing authorisation for data publication, and managing collaboration across diverse actors. Several participants also explicitly stated that their earlier barriers had been "solved." This trajectory from apprehension to problem-solving suggests a more applied approach to data use and sharing.

Behavioural intentions. Post-workshop behavioural intention data indicate a strong willingness to remain engaged in the CoP.

Table 2 summarises participants' likelihood of undertaking key CoP-related behaviours.

Table 2. *Post-workshop behavioural intentions - Bamenda (n=29)*

Behaviour / Commitment	Not at all / Slightly Likely	Somewhat Likely	Very Likely	Extremely Likely
Likelihood to use SIGE/council data	3.45%	34.48%	17.24%	44.83%
Likelihood to share datasets with CoP	10.35%	10.34%	37.48%	44.83%
Likelihood to attend quarterly meetings	3.45%	6.90%	27.59%	62.07%
Likelihood to contribute to the Regional Learning Agenda	3.45%	10.34%	13.79%	72.41%

Beyond the structured survey responses, participants made a range of concrete commitments during the plenary workshop, including: advocating for better data collection and sharing, attending quarterly CoP reflection meetings, seeking and using SIGE or council-level data to inform planning and teaching; sharing their organisations' data with the CoP, actively contributing to updating the Regional Learning Agenda, and conducting further research on foundational learning.

Workshop satisfaction and impact. Workshop feedback was strongly positive. Among post-workshop respondents (n=29), 96.55% rated the workshop 4 or 5 out of 5 for how well it met their expectations.

The panel session on the challenges of FLN was identified as the most valuable session by 32.14% of respondents, followed by the Evidence Rush session at 21.43% and the presentations on FLN (14.29%).

Regarding overall confidence in using foundational learning data, 86.21% of participants reported that their confidence had increased significantly, while the remaining 13.79% reported that it had increased somewhat. Taken together, all respondents reported at least some improvement in confidence. The workshop also performed well on the likelihood-to-recommend measure, with 64.28% of respondents awarding a score of 9 or 10.

3.4.2. Centre Region - Yaoundé CoP workshop (10 - 11 December 2025)

The Yaoundé workshop convened stakeholders to validate priorities emerging from the pre-session clinics and to jointly draft a Regional Learning Agenda and a data-sharing framework.

A total of 26 participants completed the pre-workshop survey, and 23 completed the post-workshop survey, drawn from a broad institutional cross-section that included teachers and school heads (33.33%), CSO and NGO representatives (20.83%), researchers and academics (16.67%), ministry officials (16.67%), and local authority officials (8.33%) ([↑Pambe et al., 2026](#)).

The Yaoundé cohort also brought considerable prior experience to the workshop: 57.69% had previously participated in data use or CoP initiatives related to education, a notably higher proportion than in Bamenda, and 53.85% reported more than 10 years of experience in education or FLN-related work. The majority of participants (80.77%) were based in the Mfoundi division, reflecting the workshop's location in the administrative capital.

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Knowledge gains. Pre and post-workshop survey data suggest modest but consistent shifts across the assessed knowledge domains, including understanding of the national education data system (SIGE and the Statistical Yearbook); knowledge of FLN data types available in the Centre Region; understanding of the concept and objectives of a regional CoP; familiarity with the primary focus of the Unlocking Data Initiative; and knowledge of approaches to integrating gender equity and social inclusion (GESI) in data analysis. Recognition of the Unlocking Data Initiative’s correct primary objective improved from 82.6% to 90% between pre- and post-workshop assessments. Table 3 summarises the full distribution of knowledge across pre- and post-workshop assessments.

Table 3. Knowledge distribution - Yaoundé CoP workshop (Centre Region)

Knowledge domain	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very high
National education data system (e.g., SIGE, Statistical Yearbook) Pre	7.7%	34.6%	42.3%	11.5%	3.9%
National education data system - Post	4.4%	34.6%	43.5%	13.0%	4.4%
Concept and objective of a regional CoP on FLN data - Pre	41.7%	33.3%	8.3%	16.7%	-
Concept and objective of a regional CoP on FLN data - Post	42.9%	28.6%	9.5%	19.1%	-
Primary focus of the Unlocking Data Initiative - Pre	34.6%	20.8%	29.2%	11.5%	-
Primary focus of the Unlocking Data Initiative - Post	38.1%	19.1%	28.6%	14.3%	-
Integrating equity and inclusion (GESI) in data analysis - Pre	7.7%	33.3%	34.6%	11.5%	7.7%
Integrating equity and inclusion (GESI) in data analysis - Post	9.5%	33.3%	33.3%	14.3%	9.5%

Confidence pattern: A notable and somewhat counterintuitive finding from the Yaoundé post-workshop attitudinal data was that self-reported confidence declined slightly across several dimensions compared with pre-workshop levels. This should not necessarily be

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interpreted as evidence of workshop failure; rather, it may reflect a recalibration of self-assessment following participants' more thorough exposure to the complexity of the FLN data ecosystem.

Participants may therefore have left the workshop with a more grounded, potentially more conservative understanding of their data competencies. The survey's own interpretive note explicitly observes that participants showed less confidence from pre-workshop to post-workshop, and asks why they appeared to lose confidence in their aptitude to use data in the context of the CoP. This calibration effect may indicate a more realistic assessment of capacity gaps and learning needs.

Behavioural intentions and next steps. Post-workshop, 80.96% of participants indicated that they were very interested or extremely interested in remaining actively involved in the regional CoP. A total of 73.91% expressed confidence in their readiness to participate actively in the Centre Region's Community of Practice.

Participants identified the Evidence Rush or Data Market as the most impactful session (73.91%), followed by the Regional Learning Agenda working session (60.87%), governance and next-steps discussions (56.52%), and the plenary on data context and trends (52.17%). Regarding overall improvement in knowledge and skills, 47.83% of participants reported that the workshop had improved these "a lot" (beaucoup), and a further 47.83% "quite a bit" ("assez"), for a combined 95.66% reporting a positive impact.

Participants also committed to a range of concrete actions over the following three months, organised under four broad themes: data management and accuracy, sharing and dissemination, collaboration and engagement, and capacity building.

Workshop quality ratings were consistently positive across all assessed dimensions. Table 4 below summarises participant ratings.

Table 4. Workshop quality ratings - Yaoundé CoP workshop (n=23)

Aspect	Poor	Fair	Good	Excellent
Relevance of workshop themes to participants' work	-	4.8%	52.4%	42.9%
Quality of facilitation and discussions	-	9.1%	63.6%	27.3%
Balance between presentations and interactive work	-	31.8%	40.9%	27.3%
Diversity and usefulness of stakeholder participation	-	13.6%	45.5%	40.9%
Overall organisation and logistics	-	13.6%	45.5%	40.9%

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Areas identified for improvement in future workshops included stronger time management and adherence to the programme, providing documents during the workshop rather than afterwards, offering survey instruments in both French and English, and allowing more time for thematic sessions. These recommendations were intended to inform the design of Cycle 3 CoP activities.

4. Findings and evidence progress

Cycle 2 activities generated evidence that both confirmed and refined the barriers identified in Cycle 1. These activities include:

4.1. Confirmation and deepening of Cycle 1 findings

4.1.1. Fragmented data landscape

The Evidence Rush confirmed Cycle 1's finding that the FL evidence landscape remains fragmented across institutions and sources. Data on teacher deployment is available from sources such as MINEDUB postings and council payrolls, but these sources are not harmonised, leading to what the team has termed the Needy School Paradox: official figures mask classroom realities. One regional official described this instability in practical terms:

“So today, it’s a needy school. A needy school is a school that has fewer than three teachers... Each time we think a school is no longer a needy school, the next minute, it becomes a needy school. The teachers who have been there are going on retirement, almost increasing each day because it’s an ageing workforce.”

Workshop discussions further highlighted the compounding effects of internal displacement, with overcrowding in relatively secure areas occurring alongside school depletion in crisis-affected zones. This means that apparently stable administrative figures may, in fact, reflect sharply different conditions across locations.

A second participant illustrated the same issue from a different angle:

“Last time in the national seminar, they made mention of environments in the Northwest. About three or four years ago, no government school was functioning... The teachers didn’t go away. But the children are not in school. That is why we have statistics on personnel, but not on pupils and enrolment. Zero. And the minister immediately intervened.”

These reflections underscore the importance of the CoP's work in harmonising and contextualising data across sources. Where evidence is triangulated and interpreted in context, it is more likely to support responsive decision-making; where it remains fragmented, its practical value is reduced.

4.1.2 Capacity gaps - redefined as a data literacy crisis

Cycle 1 identified capacity gaps, while Cycle 2 clarified them more precisely, identifying a deficit in data literacy and governance awareness at the subnational level. Participant reflections suggested that data work is often experienced as filling out forms rather than

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as part of a broader evidence cycle. The Regional Chief of Statistics described the structural dimensions of this gap as follows:

“Some of the headteachers are not able to read and interpret the questionnaires. So we need to train those who go out and access the rural areas... If we produce a template in Excel, we have 34 subdivisions, only about 18 or 19 will be able to manipulate the Excel template.”

This suggests that the issue is not only a matter of individual skills. It is also a structural issue, because data collection instruments assume levels of technological familiarity that many sub-national actors do not yet possess. Workshop discussion also surfaced a practical alternative to these constraints

“I understand that there are digital tools like Google Forms, like Google Connect tools, which can make it easy for these people to just put in data, instead of manipulating an Excel sheet, which will require a computer. A simple gadget like a phone can help do that and collect data. I don't know if the government is looking at anything like that.”

The discussion that followed indicated growing interest in data collection approaches that reduce the technical burden on frontline actors, such as digital tools. Taken together, this exchange illustrates the CoP's potential to surface implementation barriers and connect them to practical institutional responses.

4.1.3 Trust deficit - institutionally engineered solutions

Requests from CSOs for a safe space, together with the government's scepticism about some CSO-generated data, confirmed that trust remains a central issue in the data ecosystem. At the same time, participants also articulated a shared motivation to improve educational outcomes through collaboration.

“There is that white divide. But one thing that was clear was that all these actors want to improve education in our country, and there is nothing these actors can do on their own. Both of them need to collaborate so that we can achieve results faster.”

This shared purpose appears to have informed the design of the Safe Harbour and Shadow Report mechanisms in the Bamenda Charter, translating trust-building concerns into more formal operational rules.

4.1.4 Data quality - systemic failures exposed

Discussion of data quality moved beyond general concern to identify several systemic weaknesses in how education data is produced, reported, and used. Participants described EMIS/SIGE data as becoming outdated by the time it is aggregated, as difficult to use in settings where reporting depends heavily on connectivity, and as insufficiently

specific regarding disability categories. The data manipulation problem was given its most candid articulation by the regional chief of statistics:

“Some manipulate the data to give us inadequate data because, one, they don’t want to pay dues. Public and private agencies manipulate data for us not to know the level of statistics of their various populations because of taxes, insurance, and teachers... When we get the real data of your institution, there is a tendency that the government policy will want to know: is this school authorised?”

4.2. New, granular insights – The evidence void

- **The “Evidence Void”:** The Traffic Light assessment conducted during the Evidence Rush indicated that several strategic priorities, including motivating data sharing and disability accommodation, fall into the red category, meaning that current evidence is weak or insufficient. This limits the extent to which policy and planning can rely on existing evidence in these areas.

The significance of this gap is reinforced by the pre-workshop KAP findings, which showed low familiarity across both workshop sites with key national data systems and with approaches to integrating equity and inclusion into data analysis.

In Bamenda, 75% of participants rated their knowledge of foundational learning data sources at level 1 or 2 prior to the workshop, while in Yaoundé, 75% rated their knowledge of the CoP’s concept and objectives at the two lowest levels. Taken together, these findings suggest that the evidence gap is not merely a supply-side problem of missing datasets, but also a demand-side challenge involving potential users’ capacity to seek, interpret, and act on available evidence.

- **Context-driven barriers:** The workshops identified contextual barriers that shape how the data ecosystem operates in each region.

In the Northwest, the connectivity constraints were described as severe enough to make centralised online reporting through SIGE difficult or exclusionary in practice, helping to explain the emphasis on an Offline-First data architecture policy. This interpretation is reinforced by pre-workshop KAP data showing that 68.75% of Bamenda participants rated their confidence in reading SIGE dashboards at the two lowest levels, suggesting not only a skills gap but also the limited practical accessibility of the tools they were expected to use.

In the Centre Region, urban-rural disparities, classroom overcrowding, and the concentration of most participants in the Mfoundi division emerged as key contextual factors shaping the regional learning agenda. Post-workshop findings from Yaoundé further revealed that participants working across mixed urban-rural

settings face distinct barriers to consistent data engagement, including limited access to disaggregated data and inadequate feedback mechanisms between schools and regional planners.

- **Local ownership of decentralisation:** One notable development from the cycle was the more assertive role taken by local governance actors. Local councils, including those represented through the United Councils and Cities of Cameroon (UCCC), were described as positioning themselves as active contributors to the learning process and as calling for a “Data-for-Credits” feedback loop that would connect data submissions to more visible budget responses from the central government. This shift appears to be more than rhetorical.

Post-workshop KAP data from Bamenda shows that 82.76% of participants agreed or strongly agreed that local councils have a key role in foundational learning, while 62.07% indicated they were extremely likely to attend quarterly CoP meetings. In Yaoundé, participants from local government institutions were among those who committed to concrete data sharing and stakeholder collaboration over the next three months. Taken together, these findings suggest that sub-national actors are not simply passive recipients of centrally generated data mandates but are increasingly positioning themselves as active co-producers and co-users of foundational learning evidence.

Calibrated self-assessment as a learning indicator: The post-workshop attitudinal data from Yaoundé introduces an important insight for programme design: exposure to the complexity of the evidence ecosystem may produce a short-term recalibration of participants’ self-assessed confidence. This pattern should not be automatically interpreted as a programme failure and may instead reflect a constructive learning effect, with implications for the design of follow-up capacity support in Cycle 3.

5. Learning synthesis and adaptations

5.1. Key learnings

1. CoPs require clear, actionable mandates if they are to move from dialogue to action. The process of defining and adopting a formal Regional Learning Agenda gave the collaborative platform a clearer sense of direction and purpose.
2. Trust needs to be supported through institutional mechanisms, not only through goodwill or engineered informal collaboration. Mechanisms like the non-punitive “Safe Harbour” and formal “Shadow Report” provisions illustrate how trust concerns can be.
3. Data ecosystem diagnostics appear to work best when they are participatory and easy for diverse stakeholders to interpret. The “Traffic Light” assessment helped create a shared understanding of the strengths and gaps in the evidence across diverse stakeholder groups.
4. A uniform model is unlikely to work equally well across contexts. The findings suggest that effective frameworks need to be adapted to the regional context, with arrangements for the crisis-affected Northwest differing from those developed for the Centre Region.

5.2. Adaptations made

- **From a generic workshop to a “Clinic-to-Workshop” model:** the design shifted from a single multi-stakeholder event to a process that included pre-clinics, created safer spaces for candid input, and strengthened plenary discussions.
- **From a manifesto to binding frameworks:** the output evolved from a guiding manifesto in Cycle 1 to context-specific charters/principles with clearer operational protocols in Cycle 2.
- **Integrating offline-first design:** in response to connectivity constraints, the project’s tools and recommendations increasingly emphasised asynchronous or mobile-based data capture to improve inclusion in harder-to-reach areas.

Integrating “offline-first” design: In response to connectivity constraints, the project’s tools and recommendations increasingly emphasised asynchronous or mobile-based data capture to improve inclusion in rural areas.

6. Preliminary outcomes and indicators

Table 5. Cycle 2 preliminary outcomes and evidence of progress

Outcome area	Indicator	Evidence from Cycle 2
Advanced CoP operation	Regional Learning Agendas were defined and adopted.	Eight consensus questions were ratified in NW; the Centre Agenda was validated.
	Formal governance frameworks were established and signed.	The Bamenda Charter was ratified; the Yaoundé Principles were finalised.
	Evidence was systematically mapped and assessed.	“Traffic Light” assessment was completed for North West priorities.
Enhanced collaboration and trust	Mechanisms to address the trust deficit were co-created.	Examples include the Safe Harbour ethics compact and the Shadow Report mechanism.
	Stakeholders developed a more shared understanding of systemic barriers.	Documentation of “Needy School Paradox,” “Evidence Void,” etc.
Contextual adaptation and ownership	Frameworks were adapted to distinct regional challenges.	The North West charter addressed crisis, security, and connectivity concerns; the centre principles addressed urban-rural disparity.
	Local government actors showed greater agency in the data-for-resources loop.	UCCC called for a “Data-for-Credits” feedback loop to be incorporated into the framework.

7. Conclusion and recommendations for Cycle 3

Cycle 2 appears to have moved the regional Communities of Practice beyond their initial launch phase and toward more structured agenda-setting forms of operation. The co-creation of Regional Learning Agendas and more formal frameworks suggests progress toward sustainable and collaborative data use. The cycle also provides evidence that the DBIR approach can support adaptive management by introducing new tools and protocols that respond to lessons learned from Cycle 1.

One of the most critical findings is the extent of the evidence gap on several core priorities. The CoPs now have clearer mandates, but in several areas they still lack the evidence base needed to act on those mandates effectively. In addition, a persistent data literacy gap at the sub-national level may limit the quality and use of future evidence generation.

Recommendations for DBIR Cycle 3:

- **Generate evidence on red zone priorities:** consider a small-grants research programme that supports Master's and PhD students from regional universities to conduct primary research on the red-category questions (e.g., data-sharing incentives, disability inclusion). This would help expand the evidence base while also strengthening local research capacity.
- **Implement a tiered capacity development strategy:** move beyond general sensitisation toward more technical workshops on the data value chain, including synthesis, collection, analysis, and use, with differentiated modules for data producers and data users.
- **Pilot context-appropriate data tools:** test an offline-first or mobile-based data collection tool in a sample of schools in each region with a limited set of indicators on learning outcomes and disability inclusion.
- This could help inform national adaptations that support subnational data ecosystems, including possible revisions to SIGE protocols and stronger support for decentralised data roles.
- **Convene the national reflection event:** synthesise findings from both regional CoPs and use a national policy dialogue to present the Regional Learning Agendas, the evidence gap analysis, and any pilot results. This could help inform national adaptations that support subnational data ecosystems, including possible revisions to SIGE protocols and stronger support for decentralised data roles.
- **Strengthen CoP governance and monitoring:** support the newly formed steering committees and TWGs in holding their first implementation meetings and

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in developing a simple tracker for activities and outputs against the 90-day actions in the charters and learning agendas.

Overall, Cycle 3 should focus on narrowing the gap between identified evidence needs and practical action. By generating missing data, strengthening essential skills, and testing feasible tools, the project may help the CoPs transition from agenda-setting to producing more actionable insights that improve foundational learning outcomes in Cameroon.

References

These references are available digitally in our evidence library at <https://docs.edtechhub.org/lib/GHWE5G33>

Fotso, C., Pambe, R., & Mirabel Yuh, N. (2025). *Design-Based Implementation Research Report: Cycle 1. Improving collaboration through Communities of Practice to inform foundational learning policies in Cameroon* [Collaborative Evaluation]. Unlocking Data. <https://doi.org/10.53832/unlockingdata.1035>. Available from <https://docs.unlockingdata.africa/lib/JB98ZXEI>. Available under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. ([details](#))

Pambe, R., Fotso, C., Kelese, M., Nain, M. Y., Nashipu, S., & Okwen, P. (2026). *Strengthening System Learning Through Evidence: Inaugural Report of the Regional Community of Practice in the Northwest Region* [Learning Brief]. Unlocking data. <https://doi.org/10.53832/unlockingdata.1045>. Available from <https://docs.unlockingdata.africa/lib/RCBBEU7D>. Available under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. ([details](#))